

WAYS FOR ADJUSTING MANAGEMENT PRACTICE TO THE RECENT CHANGES ON THE INTERNATIONAL INDUSTRIAL LANDSCAPE

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Abstract

Purpose – *This paper aims to identify the recent research trends in the field of industrial management regarding the ability to adapt by resilience and sustainability under the new global challenges.*

Methodology/approach - *The present paper is a bibliographical study based on in-depth literature review of selected articles filtered by key words and abstract reading.*

Findings – *The current research trends are focusing on the new technologies paving the path to Industry 5.0 in order to mitigate unexpected and disrupting events affecting both the supply chains, and the environment, providing resilience and sustainability.*

Research limitations/implications – *The present research is limited to the sources published between 2023 – 2024, in Scopus database.*

Practical implications – *Understanding the current research trends in the industrial management for tackling the recent changes and events on the international landscape is helpful for both academia and practitioners in gaining resilience and sustainability.*

Originality/value – *Resting on the newest research work related to the major challenges of green and circular economy, digitization, supply change resilience, this paper provides the most updated synthesis on the subject.*

Key words: *resilience, production management, sustainability*

Introduction

Several new challenges have inhabited in the last few years the industrial manufacturing landscape on a global scale. Among these, we may point out on one hand the need to build up the capacity of resilience in order to mitigate so called disruptive events as “pandemic, peaking inflation, supply chain bottlenecks at the international level, and energy crises” (Narula et al., 2024), and on the other hand the need to keep pace with the new emerging technologies: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), Big data, Cyber-Physical Systems, Blockchain (Kopeinig, Woschank, and Olipp, 2024; Mallik, 2023), to mention only a few.

Beside the above challenges, issues related to the scarcity of resources (e.g. microchips), waste management difficulties, and the environmental pollution have emphasized the importance of Circular Economy and led to initiatives known under the Industry 4.0 and

Industry 5.0 paradigms, marking the shift of the focus from optimizing performance to efficiency and sustainability (Narula et al., 2024).

Under these circumstances, it becomes more and more obvious for both academics and practitioners the need to gain a comprehensive overview about the above-mentioned challenges and to understand the up-to-date ways on adapt by resilience and sustainability.

The aim of this study is to identify the most recent trends, concepts, directions and technologies in the field of academic research related to production management. Ensuing the multiple changes and disruptions that happened globally in the recent past, the efficient adaptation of systems to the environment is most often described and analyzed through the prism of resilience. Adaptive strategies that lead to prior equilibrium after experiencing a disruption, by being prepared and acting cost-effective and at the proper moment represent the ability of a system termed resilience (Cicerelli and Ravetti, 2024). Adaptive resilience is described as a system that has the capacity to identify risks, to learn and to adapt to the uncertainty and external changes from the environment (Kiss, Hetesi, and Kiss, 2024). Therefore, analyzing resilience, identifying its expressions, components, facilitating technologies to develop strategies in the management of the manufacturing industry is of extreme significance.

This article is organized as follows: in the second section we present the research methodology, in the third section we present the results of the analysis, and in the fourth section we proceed to discuss the results and meet several conclusions and figure out future research avenues.

Methodology

The database used in this research article was Scopus (www.scopus.com), accessed on 03.08.2024. This choice was met as Scopus is considered of broader coverage and better updated by several authors (Madsen, Berg, and Di Nardo, 2023).

In order to filter the amount of available sources, the authors restricted the search by including only works published between 2023 – 2024, in English language and of open access.

By using for the search query, the words “production”, “industr*”, “management”, and “resilien*” in the Article title, Abstract, Keyword, resulted in a first stage 157 articles.

In a second stage, after thoroughly reading the abstracts, articles found as being not relevant in accordance with our research’s aim, were excluded, and as a result 58 research papers qualified for an in-depth analysis. Exclusion was conducted on the differentiation according to the field of applicability, thus articles related to agro-industry, reduction of food waste, technical description of solutions for recycling electrical and plastic components, or mining were removed. Timeline restriction to 2023-2024 is argued by the need to analyze the production management resilience to the dynamic shifts on the global landscape in the recent past outlined in the introduction,

Results

Analyzing the current state of the art in the 58 selected academic works for identifying the connection between resilience and management practice in the manufacturing industry in the recent years, findings unfold along several research aspects, namely the geographical distribution of interest, research dimensions: economic, environmental, technological, social and regulatory, focus on management level and sequence, and the applied technologies upholding sustainability and resilience opportunities in production management.

Researching resilience in the management of the manufacturing industry, results show that global interest is manifested among scholars. Although half of the analyzed studies have underlined general solutions, benefits and transferable knowledge in strategic and operational management, the other half is represented by empirical research conducted on a scattered geographical area, covering countries as Sweden, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Ireland, Hungary, Czech Republic, Portugal, Spain, Canada, India, Russia, China, Ukraine, Thailand, Malaysia, Brazil, Japan, Taiwan, Iraq, Ghana and South Africa. From these studies, Italy stands out with a 12 percent representation, manifesting engagement in design-based industrial conversion (Bruno and Lerma, 2023), industrial agile working (Cimini, Lagorio, and Cavalieri, 2024), digital transformation and green supply chains (Carpitella, 2024), anthropology integration in systemic sustainability in the manufacturing sector (Fernández-Miguel et al., 2024), and digital system architecture (Aruvali, Marchi, and Rauch, 2024).

Resilience and production management in manufacturing industry is analyzed considering all dimensions: economic, environmental, technological/ informational, regulatory, social.

With the recent technology advancements and disruptions, most of the studies focus on the technological and informational perspective, representing slightly over one third of the selected core research papers. Academics and practitioners are aiming at delivering solutions for smart manufacturing by developing monitoring, control, metaverse integration, and management system architectures (Aruvali et al., 2024; Bujari et al., 2023; Van et al., 2023), integrating cloud-based and ERP in supply chain (Tinkov et al., 2023), cobots in end-of-line industrial applications (Dmytriiev, Carnevale, and Giberti, 2024), distributed ledger technologies in supply chain management (Asante et al., 2023; Hau et al., 2023), and matching AI technology solutions to identified problematic areas of the supply chain management (Kazancoglu et al., 2023). Highlighting technological solutions for the collaboration of production and software engineers (Bega et al., 2023) and for the supply chain disruption risk management (Fortes, Tenera, and Cunha, 2023; Fu et al., 2023; Huang, Wang, and Zhang, 2023) are also valuable insights.

Industry 4.0 enabling technologies as IoT, Machine Learning, AI, cyber-physical systems, augmented and virtual reality, Big Data, robotics, advanced materials or blockchain are creating flexibility and increasing productivity with concurrent sustainability and efficiency in smart factories. Researchers aligned to the European Commission's vision introduced in 2021 about Industry 5.0 (European Commission, 2021) are emphasizing the relevance and indispensability of human-centeredness when implementing Industry 4.0 technologies (Chabane, Komljenovic, and Abdul-Nour, 2023; Grosse et al., 2023; Wan and Leirmo, 2023).

Resilience and sustainability being mostly concurrently utilized concepts in the production management, the dimension of environmental research approach is also predominant, but mostly paired with the economic, technical or social dimension. The green transition to carbon neutrality and the circular economy requirements overlaying the economy affected by multiple international shocks claim to consider systematically the environmentally sustainable management strategies in the manufacturing industry. Various aspects of complexity in the electronics sector are analyzed in relation to sustainability to achieve resilience (Cicerelli and Ravetti, 2024), corporate social responsibility, green accounting and environmental auditing are proposed as solutions for waste management strategy development (Faieq and Cek, 2024), strategic opportunities are identified when integrating efficient resource management, sustainable production processes and new technologies (Lau, Turan, and Sazali, 2024), contribution of Industry 4.0 technologies to the environmental sustainability in production management is assessed (Kopeinig et al. 2024), ecological approach to sustainability and resilience is developed in the design of a production plant (Kiss et al., 2024). Environmental research of resilience in the production management is one basic approach, emphasizing the sustainability goals and resource scarcity awareness.

The economic dimension of the resilient production management focuses on analyzing supply chain disruption recovery amid Covid 19 (Fan et al., 2023), on sustainable and resilient management practices effects on product price and wage dynamics (Yeboah et al., 2023), on the macroeconomic vulnerability of national economies in the low-carbon transition process (Magacho et al., 2023) or on circular material employment strategies (Santos et al., 2024).

Part of the selected research articles are also investigating the resilient production management's regulatory dimension. It is found that flexibility, collaboration and resilience regarding regulatory measurements are key factors in times of sever challenges and crisis (Amaral et al., 2023; Howlett, Niarchou, and Naughton, 2024).

Regarding management level and sequence, the uttermost focus is shifted towards supply chain management. Research direction in this area is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Supply chain research directions in the resilient production management

Approach	Assessment	Industry	reference
Green supply chain	barriers and strategies to address them	automotive	(Carpitella 2024)
	SDGs relation to GSC management	-	(Raman et al. 2023)
Supply chain disruption	Intertwined circular SC disruption management strategy (JIT and Lean) in SC disruption	-	(Echefaj et al. 2024)
	SC disruption lessons – Covid 19	pharmaceutical	(Takawira and Poe 2024)
	SC disruption recovery after Covid 19	-	(Fan et al. 2023)
	Agility in the SC disruptions	automotive	(Křenková, Procházka, and Túry 2023)
	SC disruption risk management	automotive	(Huang et al. 2023)
	Demand risk management	semiconductor	(Fu et al. 2023)
	I.4.0 technology integration in SC management	circular SC management with distributed ledger technology using blockchain	-
cloud-based technologies/ ERP in sustainable SC		construction	(Tinkov et al. 2023)
matching AI tools as solutions to SC problematic areas		-	(Kazancoglu et al. 2023)
conceptual planning model for managing SC in I4.0 environments		-	(Reyes, Mula, and Díaz-Madroñero 2023)
SC security management through blockchain		-	(Asante et al. 2023)
Metaverse impact on SC and operation management		-	(Dolgui and Ivanov 2023)
SC strategy	Resource repurposing and product substitution	-	(Villar et al. 2024)
	Complexity in sustainability management	-	(Cicerelli and Ravetti 2024)
	supply chain management knowledge graph for large-scale product manufacturing	-	(Huang and Cheng 2024)

Progress in establishing resilience measurement tools, creating digital system architecture, risk management, waste management, distributed energy resources, human-centricity, values and forecasted trends regarding Industry 5.0, sustainability of implementing advanced technologies in circular economy are also strategy-developing research interest areas.

Discussion and conclusions

This study provides a concise overview of the up-to-date academic research on production management related to resilience and sustainability, crucial for adapting to the uncertainties of fast changing environment and to achieving progress regarding the SDGs. Concluding the results of this bibliographic study it can be asserted that resilience is a key aspect of production management efficiency and quality. Resilience as an approach emerges in research studies along with other concepts as flexibility, agility, transparency, collaboration or adaptability. Adaptive resilience in manufacturing enhanced by advanced technology is shaping the future of Industry 5.0, ensuring the efficient management of complex human-centered systems.

Advanced Industry 4.0 technology is a fundamental aspect in production management resilience built on interconnectedness, offering real-time solutions, and zero-defect manufacturing opportunity. Thus, the technical dimension of this research field is very extensive and diverse. The environmental and economic dimension is also comprehensive due to the sustainability prerequisites and is often linked to the technical – informational dimension. Worth mentioning that the social dimension regarding the production management's resilience is barely discussed, although crisis management deeply affects the social domain, as we could experience it with the Covid 19 pandemic or with the war in Ukraine.

Most researched topic is related to the supply chain management, being the most affected by the recent disruptions occurred. Other compelling topics are gaining space, as distributed energy resources, human-centricity, digital system architecture, and sustainability of Industry 4.0 technologies in the circular economy. Studies developing resilience measurement tools are paving the way for a more systematic and innovative approach to the future challenges in production management.

Limitations of this study include firstly the fact that Scopus is the only database for this research, secondly the subjectivity related to selection based on abstract analysis, and thirdly the space constraint for discussing the synthesis of such a complex and multifaced phenomenon.

Understanding the current research trends in the industrial management for tackling the recent changes and events on the international landscape structured by this study is helpful for both academia and practitioners in gaining resilience and sustainability.

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